

**ASSESSMENT OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' SATISFACTION
TOWARDS SCHOOL FACILITIES AND SERVICES DURING THE
TRANSITION TO SINGLE SHIFT FACE-TO-FACE
AND BLENDED CLASSES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 6

Pages: 656-666

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2495

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13935207

Manuscript Accepted: 09-27-2024

Assessment of Junior High School Students' Satisfaction towards School Facilities and Services During the Transition to Single Shift Face-to-Face and Blended Classes

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Abstract

This study made use of the mixed method study utilizing the quanti – quali approach in gathering the needed data for the study which included 295 students that constitutes to 10% of the total population of learners under the Junior High School Department of Bambang National High School. Finding revealed that respondents of the study claim that they are satisfied with the school facilities and services during the transition to single shift face -to- face classes. The indicators school facilities and services along tangibles, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and reliability do not differ significantly on the assessment of the Grade 8 respondents. However, significant differences were found among the Grade 7, 9, and 10 respondents. In terms of the experiences of the learners, motivation and patience became the dominant theme for their responses which indicate what they feel during the implementation of single shift face -to-face classes.

Keywords: *facilities, services, single shift face-to-face, satisfaction*

Introduction

As the COVID-19 pandemic starts to subside, Philippine schools have started to reopen their campuses to students. For many, this is a return to normality. However, we have to truly understand that this is a “new normal”, not only in the fact that we have to be aware of health and social distancing, but also with regard to how we frame our students' learning experience while the most significant changes were the increase of non-traditional students whose learning needs mostly depend on collaboration and integration, and, a rise in instructional technology that challenges teachers in the delivery of instruction (Carpena, 2016).

These changes were reinforced during the spread of Coronavirus disease in the last month of 2019 when the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the global pandemic in the first quarter of 2020 which forced governments to implement lockdown and social distancing policy that disrupted the traditional methods of teaching and learning (WHO, 2020).

In the 2015 study of St. Lawrence, they stated that majority of the students abroad agreed that it is better to attend morning classes because after the class, they would not have to worry about anything. After class, they can just relax, study or go somewhere to have some fun with their friends. They also agreed that students are fresher in the morning than in the afternoon.

Similarly, the way school schedules are currently organized is hindering student performance and that an intervention as inexpensive and simple rescheduling of classes can have a meaningful impact on students. Their study also concluded that students who are in the 10th grade in morning class, when it comes to scores in intelligence test, are significantly higher than those who are in the afternoon class. In like manner, students who wake up early for morning classes tend to get better grades for they are still active in listening to their discussions in the morning than in the afternoon. Furthermore, who took afternoon or later classes can have more sleep than those who took morning classes and they had more time to go out with friends during late nights.

The reasoning behind this is the maturity in handling the career. But this was contradicted when the effects of later classes might include more sleep but this might be offset by lower quality sleep, which in turn might affect students' ability to engage intellectually with their coursework.

Understudies with later class begin times dozed longer, experienced less daytime drowsiness, and were less inclined to miss class. Chronotype was a critical mediator of rest timetables and daytime working; those with morning inclination went to informal lodging up prior and worked better for the duration of the day. The advantages of taking later classes did not reach out to scholarly execution, be that as it may; grades were to some degree bring down in understudies with dominantly late class plans.

With schools facing increased pressure to improve teaching and learning, the duties and responsibilities of principals expanded further to include the responsibility for leading school reform that would raise student achievement. Thus, giving emphasis on the health and well - being of the learners. Success in leading reforms to increase student achievement often hinged upon a principal's ability to create a shared vision within the school community and success in implementing new organizational structures that engage teachers in shared decision-making with empirical basis through research.

Bambang National High School as a public secondary learning institution in the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya is not exempt in such dilemma having a large population of learners that increases every year. With inclusion on reasons that the facilities of the school such as classrooms have resorted to problems such as student teacher ratio. However, with the move to normalize actual school setting, the double shift that was implemented in the beginning of the school year has already been reverted to single shift classes for the Junior High School among the Grade 7, 8, and 10 in particular.

While due to the population of the Grade 9 learners a double shift blended learning, modality was implemented to address concerns regarding the availability of classrooms. Thus, to further have feedback among the learners regarding the single shift and blended learning modality. Moreover, the decrease of learner population in the 7th Grade due to the opening of Integrated Schools in the municipality has not really significantly influenced the utilization of classrooms. Since transferees on higher grade levels have increased. Furthermore, the population of Grade 9 learners have increased drastically that forced management to subject the learners into blended learning modality to further accommodate the said learners. This assessment of the Junior High School student satisfaction towards school facilities and services during the transition to single shift face - to - face & blended classes is hereby proposed to further ascertain student satisfaction on the move towards the full implementation of single shift classes for the incoming school year.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the satisfaction of the Junior High School learner's assessment on their satisfaction towards school facilities and services during the transition to single shift face - to - face and blended learning classes. Specially, this research study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learner's profile in terms of grade level?
2. What is the level satisfaction of the learners in terms of tangibles; responsiveness; empathy; assurance; reliability; and satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant difference in the learner's profile when grouped according to grade level?
4. What are the experiences of the learners during the implementation of single shift face - to - face and blended learning modality.
5. Based from the findings of the study, what plan of actions may be proposed to improve the learning delivery in school?

Literature Review

Studies show a variety of perceptions on the effect of the double session schooling system towards the comprehension level of morning and afternoon shifts. Some studies state that there is almost no correlation between the students' level of comprehension to the class schedules being utilized by the school.

While there are those studies which articulate that the performance of the students will be much better if it suits their individual preferences for the schedules of their class (Han et. al, 2012). Other than that, a certain study also says that students who are inclined toward evening schedule are more likely to exhibit characteristics that are negatively related to academic achievements unlike the students with a proclivity on morning shift that show complementary effect in which they exhibit characteristics that are positively related to academic achievement (Cavallera & Guidici, 2011).

In a memo reiterating DepEd Order No. 037, series of 2022, or the "Guidelines on the Cancellation or Suspension of Classes and Work in Schools in the Event of Natural Disasters, Power Outages/Power Interruptions, and Other Calamities," DepEd emphasized to school heads and directors that extremely high temperatures fall within the parameters of immediately canceling classes or transitioning to ADM.

Looking at links between blended learning and the heat impact of climate change, it must be noted that studies conducted as early as 2019 by the International Labor Organization had foreseen that extreme temperatures due to climate change would become a safety hazard for people living in climate change-vulnerable countries [1], but still, DepEd endorsed the return to face-to-face classes—mandatory for public schools, optional for private—citing the educational and socio-emotional benefits of direct interactions among learners, made possible as the country was gradually recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic in the final quarter of 2022.

Displaying commendable responsiveness and adaptiveness, DepEd adjusted their perspective on blended learning arrangements following reports of students experiencing heat-related health issues, such as the case in Laguna during the last week of March, when dozens of students fainted due to heat exhaustion as they stayed outdoors for their school's fire and earthquake drills.

Conversely, Pedroza (2017), claims that learners seem to do better when they attend in afternoon shift than the morning. Further emphasizing that his findings are coherent and well-grounded since these are proven in various studies and references. Furthermore, he emphasized that his findings would also stress out how comprehension levels of the students toward their major subjects are being affected by the class schedules. Furthermore, there are four views on the relationship arousing between the class schedules and the comprehension level of students furthermore he suggests that the number of shift that a school is implementing has no adverse effect on the academic achievement or the comprehension level of students which was opposed by Han et al. (2012) in which he argued that the comprehension level of students are affected in this kind of system since this type of system is not utilizing the individual preference of the learner on what schedule best suited for them.

Cavallera and Guidici (2011) on the other hand, contradicted this view in which they clearly stated that even if the schedule is match for the individual preferences of the learner this system still affects the comprehension level of learner specially during afternoon classes.

In contrast, Pedroza's (2017) affirms that the evening shift students do better than the morning shift students when it comes to academic

achievement.

Vasquez et al. (2016), explained that shifting particularly in the afternoon will widen the gap between the students in which the morning shift is far better than them due to negative factors. This negative factor as highlighted in the study of Ashong (2014), are reduced teaching time, tired students and teachers, teachers have less time for preparation and difficult to organize remedial or enrichment class. The teacher's viability will diminish in the afternoon due to fatigue and burnout in which most of the teachers are affected.

In agreement, Singadi et al. (2014), explained that in the side of the school organizations it places a gigantic weight for them. It resembles running two schools and observing of understudies and school activities is noticeably troublesome. This system has noteworthy ramifications on the nature of education that impedes and prompting indiscipline among understudies.

Blended learning (BL) is being adopted worldwide in higher education, corporate training, and K-12 education. Many have predicted that BL would "emerge as the predominant model of the future" (Watson, 2008, p. 3), become the "new traditional model" (Ross & Gage, 2006, p. 167), or the "new normal" in course delivery (Norberg, Dziuban, & Moskal, 2011, p. 207). The first section of this chapter will explore how BL is being defined and what we know about its adoption pace.

Research related to blended learning is rapidly increasing. Drysdale et al. (2013) identified and analyzed over 200 English language dissertations studying blended learning practices. Similarly, Halverson et al. (2012) identified the most cited journal articles, book chapters, books, white papers, authors, and journals publishing blended learning research, following up with a thematic analysis of the research questions and inquiry methodologies used in the studies to identify strengths and areas for future research (Halverson et al., 2014). Because fewer than 5% of the articles in the Drysdale et al. (2013) and Halverson et al. (2012, 2014) studies focused on blended learning issues and contexts outside of North America, Spring et al. (2016a, 2016b, 2017) conducted a series of studies to better understand the landscape of BL across seven worldwide regions. This group interviewed international researchers, locating the most cited articles and authors and using a network analysis to identify citation patterns and themes.

Models and taxonomies of BL may also provide guidance for practitioners. The third edition of this handbook presents several of the most prominent BL models for K-12, higher education, and corporate training contexts (Graham, 2013). The Horn and Staker (2014) taxonomy of blends, which has evolved in minor ways, continues to provide the dominant language and terminology of practitioners and advocates for K-12 blended learning. In higher education and corporate training few new models have been developed, and current models tend to focus on surface-level physical dimensions of the learning environments, with a few very general high-level pedagogical approaches. Future models to need to focus more directly on pedagogical rather than physical dimensions of the blend. Graham, Henrie, & Gibbons' (2014) systematic review of models and theory in blended learning research categorized them into three distinct types proposed by Gibbons and Bunderson (2005): explore, explain, and design.

While on the integration of blended - learning modality as an alternative to time that is sacrificed in the conduct of two shift classes. In reference to this Adefuin (2017), stated that blended learning served as intervention to senior high school students which provided an innovation to support teaching-learning through integration of online class and workshop activities in facilitating classes of Practical Research 1 subject in senior high school. The intervention provided empowerment both to teachers and students which allow them to have flexible time to submit assignments, participate online discussions and take online quizzes anytime anywhere. Furthermore, Adefuin (2018) claimed that the class facilitation in Understanding Culture Society and Politics subject with the fix schedule access of the created online class in computer laboratory using the learning management system contributed to improvement of exam score of the senior high school students. These shows that blended learning has a positive impact to senior high school students.

A blended learning framework produced by Clayton Christensen Institute, California in California, United States of America but was implemented in a primary level or grade schools Clayton Christensen Institute (2018). The study conducted by Clayton Christensen Institute, California the book of Michael B. Horn and Heather Staker, blended: Using Disruptive Innovation to Improve Schools San Francisco: the majority of blended-learning programs resemble one of four models: Rotation, Flex, A La Carte, and Enriched Virtual. The Rotation model includes four sub-models: Station Rotation, Lab Rotation, Flipped Classroom, and Individual Rotation.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the mixed-method utilizing the quantitative and qualitative design of research. The quantitative design was utilized through the descriptive method of research. As explained by Clause (2013) the descriptive research method is used when the researcher wants to describe specific behavior as it occurs in the environment. There are a variety of descriptive research methods available, and once again, the nature of the question that needs to be answered drives which method is used.

In this study, the descriptive approach was employed in the assessment of both participants in answering the given assessment tools. In order to acquire qualitative support on the quantitative data, interviews were conducted in order to scaffold the quantitative findings through eliciting the experiences of the participants during the implementation of single shift face - to - face classes.

Furthermore, findings from this study was utilized in enhancing the implementation of single shift face - to - face classes.

Respondents

Simple random sampling was utilized in identifying the participants of the research study. 10% of learners were randomly selected per grade level in order to acquire the number of participants needed in the study.

Table 1. *Respondents Profile*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Grade 7	66	22.37
Grade 8	73	24.74
Grade 9	80	27.11
Grade 10	76	25.76
Total	295	100

Instrument

The researcher crafted a research proposal using an adopted satisfaction of facility service quality survey checklist from Nguyen et al. (2021) in their study entitled assessment of student's satisfaction of facility service quality in private universities which has indicators along tangibles, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, reliability, and satisfaction.

Procedure

The proposal was subjected to scrutiny through evaluation from the Division Research Committee. After complying with the recommendations and necessary revisions the researcher incorporated all corrections in the research proposal before finalizing it for submission to the Division Office. After which the researcher sought permission from the Division Office through the office of the Senior Education Program Specialist for Planning and Research to release of permit to conduct research. The researcher then administered the instruments of the study. After administering the research tools the proponent will code and tabulate the raw data for the study.

After the coding and tabulation of data, statistical treatment was employed. The statistical data for the study were presented on tables to be interpreted by the proponents in order to identify the salient data which will help in developing an intervention activity for the participants of the study.

Ethical Considerations

The information acquired will be kept anonymous and will only be used for research reasons to help Bambang National High School in enhancing its single shift face - to - face modality, thus, improving the implementation of single shift face - to - face classes despite of the shortages of classrooms. At the same time findings from this study may serve as reference for other school who are experiencing similar challenges in implementing single shift classes.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Summary Table of Grade 7 Assessment*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>MPS</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Tangibles	3.15	Moderately Agree
Responsiveness	3.62	Agree
Empathy	3.65	Agree
Assurance	4.04	Agree
Reliability	3.68	Agree
Satisfaction	3.56	Agree
Overall Mean	3.62	Agree

Table 2 shows that the Grade 7 participants show a positive level of agreement in terms of their satisfaction on assurance (4.04); reliability (3.68); empathy (3.65); responsiveness (3.62); and satisfaction (3.56). Furthermore, a moderate level of agreement was gleaned in terms of tangibles with a mean score of 3.15. While in terms of their overall level of satisfaction. It is shown to be positive as gleaned on their overall level of agreement of 3.62.

Assurance

Along assurance the states that the teachers have a working spirit, is considerate, are always ready to guide and answer student questions reasonably (4.29); teaching and non - teaching personnel always do their job right (4.05); and the number of services offered by the schools are reasonable and are implemented for the benefit of the learners (3.78).

Reliability

In terms of the participants assessment of the reliability of school facilities they claim that the Programs and activities are provided exactly as committed (3.80); information related to learning and activities are fully and promptly provided to the students (3.76); and

time to give feedback on learners are done on time (3.47).

Empathy

In terms of the participants assessment along empathy the school regularly organizes to collect student's opinions on the quality assessment of living and learning conditions (3.80); student's questions and feedback are listened to, responded to, and handled quickly and properly by the school (3.67); and the school regularly checks and evaluates the quality of facilities for the learners (3.47).

Responsiveness

Along responsiveness the participants assessment states that the management staff is capable of working, managing, and serving well (3.67); the school has complete, convenient, and easy-to-search information and instruction charts (3.65); and the school regularly organizes the repair and maintenance of facilities (3.53).

Satisfaction

In terms of satisfaction, the results show that the students are satisfied with the commitment and effort of the school (3.82); students are satisfied with the facilities of the school (3.60); and students are satisfied with the schools' service attitude (3.27).

Table 3. Summary Table of Grade 8 Assessment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>MPS</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Tangibles	3.50	Agree
Responsiveness	3.58	Agree
Empathy	3.52	Agree
Assurance	3.80	Agree
Reliability	3.89	Agree
Satisfaction	3.57	Agree
Overall Mean	3.64	Agree

The above table shows that the Grade 8 participants agrees on the reliability (3.89), assurance (3.80), responsiveness (3.58), satisfaction (3.57), empathy (3.52), and tangibles (3.50). It is shown to be positive as gleaned on their overall level of agreement of 3.64.

Reliability

Findings reveal along reliability that the school programs and activities are provided exactly as committed (3.99); information related to learning and activities are fully and promptly provided to the students (3.96); and the time to give feedback on learners are done on time (3.73).

Assurance

In terms of assurance, the participants believe that the teachers working spirit is considerate, are always ready to guide and answer student questions reasonably (4.18); The number of services offered by the schools are reasonable and are implemented for the benefit of the learners (3.67); and the teaching and non - teaching personnel always do their job right (3.55).

Responsiveness

Along responsiveness, the participants believe that the management staff is capable of working, managing, and serving well (3.69); the school has complete, convenient, and easy-to-search information and instruction charts (3.66); and the school regularly organizes the repair and maintenance of facilities (3.39).

Empathy

Along empathy, the participants believe that Students questions and feedback are listened to, responded to, and handled quickly and properly by the school (3.63); the school regularly checks and evaluates the quality of facilities for the learners (3.48); and the school regularly organizes to collect student's opinions on the quality assessment of living and learning conditions (3.46).

Tangibles

In terms of tangibles, the participants assessed that the school information system and social media page are regularly updated and easy to access (3.93); the number of classrooms is guaranteed, clean, well - ventilated, and fully equipped (3.37); and the electricity and water system are fully provided and convenient (3.12).

Table 4 shows that the Grade 9 participants agreement on their satisfaction level of school facilities along assurance (4.08); reliability (3.97); empathy (3.85); tangibles and responsiveness (3.81); and satisfaction (3.70) with an overall mean score of 3.87.

Assurance

In terms of assurance, the participants show satisfaction through the following statements the teachers have a working spirit, is considerate, are always ready to guide and answer student questions reasonably (4.30); the number of services offered by the schools

are reasonable and are implemented for the benefit of the learners (4.00); and the teaching and non - teaching personnel always do their job right (3.95).

Table 4. Summary table for Grade 9 assessment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>MPS</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Tangibles	3.81	Agree
Responsiveness	3.81	Agree
Empathy	3.85	Agree
Assurance	4.08	Agree
Reliability	3.97	Agree
Satisfaction	3.70	Agree
Overall Mean	3.87	Agree

Reliability

Along reliability, the participants showed their satisfaction on the following statements. Information related to learning and activities are fully and promptly provided to the students (4.09); programs and activities are provided exactly as committed (4.14); and the time to give feedback on learners are done on time (3.69).

Empathy

In terms of the participants satisfaction along empathy, findings reveal that students' questions and feedback are listened to, responded to, and handled quickly and properly by the school (3.92); the school regularly organizes to collect student's opinions on the quality assessment of living and learning conditions (3.88); and the school regularly checks and evaluates the quality of facilities for the learners (3.76).

Tangibles

Along tangibles the participants state that the electricity and water system are fully provided and convenient (3.64); the number of classrooms is guaranteed, clean, well - ventilated, and fully equipped (3.42); and the school information system and social media page are regularly updated and easy to access (3.36).

Responsiveness

In terms of responsiveness the participants convey that the management staff is capable of working, managing, and serving well (3.93); the school has complete, convenient, and easy-to-search information and instruction charts (3.86); and the school regularly organizes the repair and maintenance of facilities (3.62).

Satisfaction

In terms of satisfaction, the participants state that the students are satisfied with the commitment and effort of the school (4.07); students are satisfied with the facilities of the school (3.55); and students are satisfied with the schools' service attitude (3.49).

Table 5. Summary table for Grade 10 assessment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>MPS</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Tangibles	3.55	Agree
Responsiveness	3.76	Agree
Empathy	3.62	Agree
Assurance	4.16	Agree
Reliability	3.96	Agree
Satisfaction	3.73	Agree
Overall Mean	3.80	Agree

Table 5 shows the facility satisfaction of the Grade 10 participants which shows that their agreement along the area of assurance (4.16); reliability (3.96); responsiveness (3.76); empathy (3.62); and tangibles (3.55) with an overall mean score of 3.80.

Assurance

In terms of the participants satisfaction along assurance wherein the findings reveal that the teachers have a working spirit, is considerate, are always ready to guide and answer student questions reasonably (4.42); the number of services offered by the schools are reasonable and are implemented for the benefit of the learners (4.16); and the teaching and non - teaching personnel always do their job right (4.06).

Reliability

The participants assessed their satisfaction along reliability through conveying that the information related to learning and activities are fully and promptly provided to the students (4.09); programs and activities are provided exactly as committed (4.09); and the time to give feedback on learners are done on time (3.70).

Responsiveness

In terms of responsiveness the participants convey that the management staff is capable of working, managing, and serving well (4.12); the school has complete, convenient, and easy-to-search information and instruction charts (3.73); and the school regularly organizes the repair and maintenance of facilities (3.43).

Satisfaction

In terms of satisfaction, the participants state that the students are satisfied with the commitment and effort of the school (4.19); students are satisfied with the school's service attitude (3.55); and students are satisfied with the facilities of the school (3.45).

Empathy

In terms of the participants satisfaction along empathy, findings reveal that the school regularly checks and evaluates the quality of facilities for the learners (3.67); the school regularly organizes to collect student's opinions on the quality assessment of living and learning conditions (3.60); and students' questions and feedback are listened to, responded to, and handled quickly and properly by the school (3.58).

Tangibles

Along tangibles the participants state that the school information system and social media page are regularly updated and easy to access (4.31); the number of classrooms is guaranteed, clean, well - ventilated, and fully equipped (3.19); and electricity and water system are fully provided and convenient (3.15).

Table 6. *Multivariate Analysis on the Differences on the Students Satisfaction towards Facilities and Services during the Transition to Single Shift Face – to – Face and Blended Classes*

Grade Level	Indicators	Mean	F-value	P-value	Remarks
Grade 7	Tangibles	3.15			
	Responsiveness	3.62	7.96	.00	Sig.
	Empathy	3.65			
	Assurance	4.04			
	Reliability	3.68			
Satisfaction	3.56				
Grade 8	Tangibles	3.50			
	Responsiveness	3.58	1.66	.13	N. Sig.
	Empathy	3.52			
	Assurance	3.80			
	Reliability	3.89			
Satisfaction	3.57				
Grade 9	Tangibles	3.81	8.35	.00	Sig.
	Responsiveness	3.81			
	Empathy	3.85			
	Assurance	4.08			
	Reliability	3.97			
Grade 10	Satisfaction	3.70			
	Tangibles	3.55			
	Responsiveness	3.76	4.87	.00	Sig.
	Empathy	3.62			
	Assurance	4.16			
Reliability	3.96				
Satisfaction	3.73				

The multivariate analysis of variance was conducted to compare the mean perception of the respondents per grade level. The multivariate result was significant per grade level (Wilk's Lambda = 0.71, $F = 5.10$, $P < 0.05$), indicating significant difference in the assessment learner's satisfaction on school facilities according to grade level. The univariate analysis showed no significant differences among the Grade 8 learners ($F = 1.66$, $P > 0.05$). However, F – tests revealed that significant differences on the following Grade 7 ($F = 7.96$, $P < 0.05$), Grade 9 ($F = 8.35$, $P < 0.05$), and Grade 10 ($F = 4.87 < 0.05$).

While there are those studies which articulate that the performance of the students will be much better if it suits their individual preferences for the schedules of their class (Han et. al, 2012). Other than that, a certain study also says that students who are inclined toward evening schedule are more likely to exhibit characteristics that are negatively related to academic achievements unlike the students with a proclivity on morning shift that show complementary effect in which they exhibit characteristics that are positively

related to academic achievement (Cavallera & Guidici, 2011).

In agreement, Singadi et al. (2014), explained that in the side of the school organizations it places a gigantic weight for them. It resembles running two schools and observing of understudies and school activities is noticeably troublesome. This system has noteworthy ramifications on the nature of education that impedes and prompting indiscipline among understudies.

Displaying commendable responsiveness and adaptiveness, DepEd adjusted their perspective on blended learning arrangements following reports of students experiencing heat-related health issues, such as the case in Laguna during the last week of March, when dozens of students fainted due to heat exhaustion as they stayed outdoors for their school's fire and earthquake drills.

Conversely, Pedroza (2017), claims that learners seem to do better when they attend in afternoon shift than the morning. Further emphasizing that his findings are coherent and well-grounded since these are proven in various studies and references. Furthermore, he emphasized that his findings would also stress out how comprehension levels of the students toward their major subjects are being affected by the class schedules.

Table 7. *Learners Experiences on the usage of Facilities and Services during the Transition to Single Shift Face – to – Face and Blended Classes*

Categories	Associated Concepts
Motivation	Personal disposition, encouragement, relationship with teachers.
Patience	Availability of resources, compromise, tolerance, acceptance.

The dominant category most frequently referred to in the respondent's accounts regarding their experiences was "motivation" which serves as a common theme for personal disposition, encouragement, relationship with teachers. However, another theme surfaced which is "patience" which serves as a common representation for availability of resources, compromise, tolerance, acceptance.

The thematic codes that were identified represents the accounts of the respondents which is stipulated by the statements of the following responses:

Motivation

Basta para sa akin OK na lang kung anong meron. Basta makapag aral lang ako. (I am contented with what we have. I just want to study) Respondent G10

Papasok na lang ako kasi sabi nang nanay at tatay ko na mahirap ang walang pinag aralan. (I will go to school because my parents told me that it's difficult to be uneducated) Respondent G10

Kahit kulang kami sa kagamitan. Mababait at maalalahanin naman ang mga teacher naming. (Even if we lack resources. At least, our teachers are kind and understanding) Respondent G8

Nahihirapan kami minsan dahil mainit lalo na at hindi gumagana mga electric fan tapos madami kami sa klase. (We are having difficulty because of the heat and we are many in the classroom) Respondent G9

Patience

Kung anong meron, yun na lang mas maganda kesa wala. (Just be contented on what we have. Its better than nothing.) Respondent G8

Mahirap maghanap ng wala kaya kung anong meron yun na. (It's difficult to look for nothing. Just be contented on what is present.) - Respondent G9

Pinagchachagaan ko na lang kung anong meron. Ang mahalaga may natututunan ako. (I just compromise on what is present. At least, I am learning) Respondent G10

Nasa public ako kaya kung anong meron at kayang ibigay tanggapan na lang. (I'm in the public, so better accept what we have) Respondent G10

As explained by Finot (2011), there are four views on the relationship arousing between the class schedules and the comprehension level of students furthermore he suggests that the number of shift that a school is implementing has no adverse effect on the academic achievement or the comprehension level of students which was opposed by Han et al. (2012) in which he argued that the comprehension level of students are affected in this kind of system since this type of system is not utilizing the individual preference of the learner on what schedule best suited for them.

Cavellera & Guidici (2011) on the other hand, contradicted this view in which they clearly stated that even if the schedule is match for the individual preferences of the learner this system still affects the comprehension level of learner specially during afternoon classes.

In contrast, Pedroza's (2017) affirms that the evening shift students do better than the morning shift students when it comes to academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, the following conclusions were drawn the respondents of the study claim that they are satisfied with the school facilities and services during the transition to single shift face -to- face classes. The indicators school facilities and services along tangibles, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and reliability do not differ significantly on the assessment of the Grade 8 respondents. However, significant differences were found among the Grade 7, 9, and 10 respondents. In terms of the experiences of the learners, motivation and patience became the dominant theme for their responses which indicate what they feel during the implementation of single shift face -to- face classes.

Based on the above conclusions, the following recommendations were drawn provision and /or orientation for Alternative Delivery Modalities be conducted before the beginning of the school year. Likewise, continuous conduct of facilities inspection should be conducted monthly in order to identify school equipment and facilities that are no longer functioning well for maintenance and repair purposes. Inclusion of alternative activities are recommended in order to address the discomfort of the learners due to the summer heat and congestion of learners inside the classroom. The provision of alternative activities that will lead to the familiarity of learners on facilities and tools that are lacking in school may be integrated in classroom discussion with visual presentations that will help enhance the theoretical mastery of the learners on the use of lacking equipment and facilities.

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